

Search filter: All adult (19+ years)

"young adult"[MeSH Terms] OR "young adult*"[Title/Abstract] OR "young person*"[Title/Abstract] OR "young individual*"[Title/Abstract] OR "young people*"[Title/Abstract] OR "young population*"[Title/Abstract] OR "young man"[Title/Abstract] OR "young men"[Title/Abstract] OR "young male*"[Title/Abstract] OR "young boy*"[Title/Abstract] OR "young woman"[Title/Abstract] OR "young women"[Title/Abstract] OR "young female*"[Title/Abstract] OR "young girl*"[Title/Abstract] OR "youngster*"[Title/Abstract] OR "youth*"[Title/Abstract] OR "juvenile*"[Title/Abstract] OR "high education"[Title/Abstract] OR "higher education"[Title/Abstract] OR "adult"[MeSH Terms] OR "adult*"[Title/Abstract] OR "middle aged"[Title/Abstract] OR "aged"[MeSH Terms] OR "aged"[Title/Abstract] OR "ageing"[Title/Abstract] OR "aging"[Title/Abstract] OR "over 65"[Title/Abstract] OR "over 70"[Title/Abstract] OR "over 75"[Title/Abstract] OR "aged, 80 and over"[MeSH Terms] OR "over 80"[Title/Abstract] OR "over 85"[Title/Abstract] OR "over 90"[Title/Abstract] OR "frail elderly"[MeSH Terms] OR "frailt*"[Title/Abstract] OR "elder*"[Title/Abstract] OR "older"[Title/Abstract] OR "oldest*"[Title/Abstract] OR "old age"[Title/Abstract] OR "septuagenar*"[Title/Abstract] OR "octogenar*"[Title/Abstract] OR "nonagenar*"[Title/Abstract] OR "centenar*"[Title/Abstract] OR "senil*"[Title/Abstract] OR "senescenc*"[Title/Abstract] OR "geriatrics"[MeSH Terms] OR "geriatric*"[Title/Abstract] OR "gerontolog*"[Title/Abstract]

Own filter extensively in PubMed tested with different sets of gold standard articles in research projects